

THE IMPORTANCE AND RELEVANCE OF MUSIC

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Annotation. *In this article, I would like to show how important music and art are in human life. It is also the main factor that gives a person aesthetic pleasure and nourishes the human soul.*

Based on their abilities, they try to work in the direction or style they want, and when determining their abilities, they are divided into directions based on their interests.

Keywords: *Music, art, nature, aesthetics, ability, emotional, composer.*

Music is such an art form that unites people through their feelings and emotional feelings.

It becomes a means of communication between them. The fact that music created by one composer evokes various experiences in the hearts of other people can be called a miracle in itself. Musical education is a component of aesthetic education. One of the leading factors shaping the human personality is education. Aesthetic education, as its component, is based on the doctrine of the essence of beauty, the unity of aesthetic and moral feelings, the popular nature of art, and expands and deepens students' knowledge of the objective world, develops their creative abilities and talents, and helps them to embody high spiritual qualities.

Usually, the goal of aesthetic education is understood to be the development of aesthetic feelings and thoughts in children, the ability to see beauty and enjoy it. In fact, the goals and objectives of aesthetic education are not limited to this, it teaches students to understand and see beauty and ugliness, highness and lowliness, joy and sorrow. Aesthetic education serves to establish universal and national values. Obviously, education affects the human mind, feelings, imagination, beliefs, worldview, actions, and behavior. The language of music is understandable and close to everyone.

Music reflects thoughts and feelings through sound waves, expresses moral problems that have been stirring humanity at different stages of life. This also reveals the philosophical essence of music. Great musical works are imbued with deep philosophical content, music reflects issues such as life and death, individuality and society, goodness and oppression, power and weakness.

The endless possibilities of music's influence on the human psyche have long attracted the attention of musicologists, thinkers and scientists. Philosophers, psychologists, educators and public figures in the arts. have tried to determine the characteristics of music that affect the formation of a person as a person. Since ancient times, there have been ideas about the influence of music, especially its components - rhythm and melody, on a person's mood, changing his inner world. -Music, as an important factor in aesthetic education, has a strong influence on the formation of the personality.

Organizing music lessons in the family, kindergarten, and school in a purposeful manner is an effective way to enrich the inner world of the younger generation and correctly understand art.

Music expresses human emotions, dreams, hopes, and desires in its own artistic language and actively affects a person's emotions. Music is both a science and an art. It is based on physics and mathematics, which turn music into a science. However, a musical work cannot be viewed as a static concept of this science.

Because music is a living art that is always developing. The art of music has become a companion of a person from the first years of his life, making a significant contribution to his general cultural development. Music is a constant companion of human life. According to the scientist Stendhal, music is the only art form that can penetrate deep into the human heart and reflect his inner experiences. "Music is included in the system of expressive types of art. Music also reflects events expressively. But it is not determined by the dimensions of space and material objects, as in architecture.

The influence of music on a person, its role in the spiritual life of an individual and society is a complex problem. This complexity and multifacetedness did not immediately come to science.

In this regard, it is appropriate to recall the words of Asafev: "...music is both art, science, language, and play." So, the role of music in the formation of musical and personal qualities of children is incomparable. Music has a comprehensive effect on a person: the melody and its musical expression deeply affect a person's emotions, awaken various feelings in him, create various moods. The text, the ideological content of the song affect not only the emotions, but also the minds of the listeners, exciting them and forcing them to think. It evokes in people a certain attitude towards the spiritual problems reflected in the work. Such an effect is extremely complex and powerful. Conditions for the development of musical abilities.

Ability is an individual characteristic of a person, which is considered a subjective condition for the successful implementation of a certain type of activity. Ability is manifested in the process of activity. Psychology shows that a human child is born not with ready-made abilities, but with abilities that are a source of realization and development of any abilities. Ability cannot develop on its own; a favorable environment is needed for its development. A child may be born with musical abilities, but if a favorable environment is not created for the formation of his musical qualities, his musical abilities will not develop. One of the leading factors in the formation of a person as a person is the environment. The environment is understood as the sum of external events that affect a person.

The aesthetic and emotional environment creates emotional comfort for the child in the world of music and forms an interest in creativity in him. However, the effectiveness of the musical environment depends not only on external conditions, but also on communication, musical-theoretical knowledge, and creative methods that regulate the musical development of the child.

In order for the process of musical education of students to be effective, there must be: socio-cultural activity of a person, reflected in the areas of abilities (E.A. Bodina); ways of accumulating social and personal experience, preserving culture (A.L. Arnoldov, L.P. Bueva, E.S. Makaryan, V.M. Mejuev); defining activity (L.S. Vygotsky); aesthetic experience associated with emotions and figurative thinking, concepts associated with artistic information (A.E. Lazar); connection with the world of people and things (V.S. Mukhina); knowledge of activities and striving for further development (V.A. Petrovsky). According to V.V. Bogoslovsky, abilities are a synthesis of human personality traits that meet the requirements of activity and ensure high results in it. V.V. Bogoslovsky also divides abilities into types depending on their direction and field.

In this regard, psychology mainly distinguishes between general and special abilities.

By general abilities is meant a system of personal characteristics that provide relative ease and productivity when mastering knowledge and applying various types of activity, the psychologist believes. Abilities are not skills, qualifications and knowledge, but the dynamics of their assimilation. Abilities are opportunities that manifest themselves in the course of activity.

Musical abilities can be developed only through musical practice, musical material, and special methods inherent in the art of music. Only music awakens a person's musical feelings. V.N. Shatskaya has repeatedly emphasized the need to cultivate the ability to feel and understand music in students.

Providing musical education, nurturing the musical abilities and talents inherent in each child, and forming the mental, physiological, labor and aesthetic qualities of the student are carried out precisely through the art of music, through musical education and upbringing, which is built into a certain system, says the scientist. People who have not received musical education do not have musical abilities. Because they have not mastered musical knowledge. Students are familiar with music before they come to school, but the mastery of musical knowledge falls on the primary grades of continuous education - general secondary education.

Because the mental aspects of a primary school student - memory, consciousness, attention, thinking are ready to master knowledge. B.M. Teplov in his work "Psychology of Musical Abilities" divides musical abilities in musical and pedagogical practice into three main groups: musical hearing - the ability to emotionally distinguish the tone functions of sounds in a melody, the expressiveness of sound. sense of rhythm - the ability to feel the expression of musical rhythm and actively (with actions) reflect musical experiences, musical memory (remembering and restoring musical information).

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Children's memories are very well developed, but their attention does not stay in one place during the lesson. School-age children perform creative tasks well. They can come up with small melodies in different rhythms, analyze songs, express music through pictures, and demonstrate their abilities. Children of this age demonstrate high musicality, which is the ability to feel rhythm, that is, the ability to emotionally respond to music, as well as the ability to distinguish music with a subtle taste, that is, the ability to hear music. The musical abilities of students are manifested in activities in the lesson (workshop). At the same time, they learn to distinguish works, distinguish their opposites and similarities, compare parts, and understand the relationships between sound, rhythm, and dynamics. In this process, their ability to play a musical composition, feel rhythm, and perform grows. Children are able to reflect their imagination based on the melodies and songs they hear and perceive.

All this is done in music lessons (trainings) and music circles. Analyzing the main forms of musical ability, one can distinguish the perception of melody and harmony. They are based on three abilities: 1. There is a sense of pitch, which is called the perceptive and emotional part of musical hearing. The sense of pitch, that is, the ability to emotionally feel the melody, the pitch function of sounds or to emotionally feel the expression of the up-down movement of sounds. This ability is otherwise called the emotional or perceptive part of musical hearing.

Solfeggio lessons are held in specialized music schools to develop musical hearing. A sense of musical rhythm is the ability to actively experience music, emotionally feel the expressiveness of musical rhythm and accurately perform it. The development of a sense of rhythm is one of the most complex abilities.

The three abilities listed above are based on the ability to feel the pitch of sounds and experience the expressive content of rhythmic patterns. Although these abilities are the main abilities necessary for musical activity, the complex of abilities does not end there. One of the main signs of musical ability is the ability to feel the expressiveness of a certain content. Based on theory and practice, it can be said that the problem of musical abilities and their development is one of the urgent problems of pedagogy and psychology. The development of these abilities also depends on the social environment, natural talent, talent, willpower, activity of the individual, physical and mental processes. Therefore, taking into account the early manifestation of musical abilities in children, as well as the fact that their abilities are formed under the influence of education and the environment, we have come to the following conclusion: Musical abilities serve as an important factor in the development of performing skills in music classes (lessons) in the system of continuous education.

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